

Virga-Sniffer Configuration for the Barbados Cloud Observatory

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1 Introduction

The Virga-Sniffer is a Python package tool developed by Kalesse-Los et al. (2023) that serves as a profile-based detection scheme for identifying precipitation, virga, and clouds using observations of vertically pointing cloud radar reflectivity and ceilometer measurements of CBH. The detection process relies on a set of empirical thresholds, which have been manually adjusted for this study using the Cloudnet data from the Barbados Cloud Observatory (BCO). This technical note summarizes the configuration of the Virga-Sniffer tool employed in Roschke et al. (2024).

2 Virga-Sniffer configurations

The cloud radar data is fundamental to the Virga-Sniffer as it establishes the temporal and vertical resolution for the detection algorithm. Specifically, for the BCO dataset, CORAL cloud radar data were taken from the Cloudnet target categorization dataset with a temporal and vertical resolution of 30 s and 30 m, respectively. As further Virga-Sniffer input, information about the cloud base height (CBH) is taken from the ceilometer.

The default configuration in Table 1 (configuration 0) summarizes all configuration flags, thresholds, and settings used for the EUREC⁴A dataset from the RV *Meteor* described in (Kalesse-Los et al., 2023). Configuration 1 contains the selection of the flags and threshold values selected for the BCO data set. The cloud and precipitation statistics between the object-based and profile-based methods show considerable differences. To increase the comparability of the two methods, two additional configurations were tested for the EUREC⁴A data set from RV *Meteor* (configuration 2 and configuration 3).

We adjusted the Virga-Sniffer configurations for the RV *Meteor* to quantify the effect when the LCL is not used to replace the lowest CBH (configuration 2 in Table 3). We also reduced the CBH smoothing window to 15 s and set the CBH cleaning threshold to 1 %, which additionally results in more high clouds being included in the statistics. This reduces the proportions of warm clouds and trade wind cumuli for configuration 3 compared to configuration 2. Using these changes to the original Virga-Sniffer settings reduces the proportion of virga from trade wind cumuli to 24 % (when using the profile-based detection method, configuration 2) and thus makes the profile-based and object-based results more comparable. Configuration 4 contains the same thresholds as configuration 1, and a new parameter selection for the clutter-mask. The clutter-mask has been adjusted so that the proportion of clutter for negative mean Doppler velocity is increased. This is further explained in Sect. 2.2.

A complete description of the individual configuration parameters can be found in the Virga-Sniffer documentation (Witthuhn et al., 2022).

2.1 Cloud base height detection

In this study, BCO Cloudnet data is used as primary input of CBH for the Virga-Sniffer. Gaps in CBH data are filled from the ceilometer internal CBH detection algorithm. Consequently, merging both CBH products increases the time steps with CBH as an input for the Virga-Sniffer CBH processing.

The Virga-Sniffer is configurable by selecting different flags and threshold values to recognize virga from the given input data. CBH is assigned to layers that are separated by the threshold of 1000 m (`cbh_layer_thres`; see Table 1). Reducing the threshold would allow a finer separation of different CBH layers in a multi-layer cloud situation. However, a lower separation threshold may lead to an increase in cloud

Table 1. Virga-Sniffer configurations: configuration 0 refers to the original configuration for the RV *Meteor* used in Kalesse-Los et al. (2023) and configuration 1 was taken for the processing of the Virga-Sniffer data for the BCO dataset. Configurations 2 and 3 are optional and will lead to more comparable results when using the profile-based compared to the object-based statistical approach developed in this study.

configuration		0	1	2	3	4
Flags						
cbh_connect2top		False	False	False	False	False
lcl_replace_cbh		True	False	False	False	False
require_cbh		True	True	True	True	True
mask_clutter		True	True	True	True	True
mask_rain		True	True	True	True	True
mask_rain_ze		True	True	True	True	True
mask_vel		True	True	True	True	True
Cloud base preprocessing		units	threshold values			
cbh_smooth_window	s	60	60	15	15	60
lcl_smooth_window	s	300	300	300	300	300
cbh_layer_thres	m	500	1000	500	500	1000
cbh_clean_thres	%	0.05	0.02	0.05	0.01	0.02
cbh_fill_limit	s	60	60	60	60	60
minimum_rangegate_number	-	2	2	2	2	2
Special configurations						
cbh_fill_method		slinear 2, 1, 3, 1,	slinear 2, 0, 1, 0,	slinear 2, 1, 3, 1,	slinear 1, 0, 2, 0,	linear 2, 0, 1, 0,
cbh_processing		4, 2, 1, 3, 1, 4, 5	2, 0, 3, 1, 0, 2, 0, 3, 4	4, 2, 1, 3, 1, 4, 5	1, 0, 2, 4	2, 0, 3, 1, 0, 2, 0, 3, 4
Virga-detection-specific		units	threshold values			
cloud_max_gap	m	150	150	150	150	150
precip_mask_gap	m	700	200	700	700	200
vel_thres	m s^{-1}	0	0	0	0	0
ze_thres	dBZ	0	0	0	0	0
clutter_c	m s^{-1}	-8	-6	-6	-6	-38
clutter_m	m s^{-1}	4	-8	-8	-8	-55

edges that become disconnected from a cloud object. This effect is particularly evident for trade wind cumulus clouds with stratiform outflow layers, where the CBH variation is large.

Before virga is detected by the Virga-Sniffer, the CBH input data is pre-processed in order to define separate layers of CBH by height. This is done by individually configurable modular methods applied to the input data. In general, the modules enable sorting CBHs into the corresponding layers, creating or merging new layers. CBH within a layer is smoothed over a certain period (defined by `cbh_smooth_window`). Optionally, the lowest CBH layer can be replaced by the LCL, but this is prevented in this study by setting `lcl_replace_cbh = False`. A detailed explanation of CBH processing can be found in Kalesse-Los et al. (2023).

An example of the Virga-Sniffer output can be seen in Fig. 1 (b) together with the Cloudnet target classification (a) for BCO observations on 2 December 2021. Note that there is a large proportion of pixels misclassified as "Drizzle or rain" by Cloudnet below shallow cumulus clouds after 07:15 UTC that are mostly unclassified radar signals with radar reflectivity factor below -50 dBZ in the Virga-Sniffer output. Also

note that for this case study the CBH of the Virga-Sniffer tool differs from the CBH in Cloudnet (Fig. 1). In this case, the differences in CBH are due to the configurations of the Virga-Sniffer, where the LCL is used to fill gaps in the first CBH layer (`LCL_replace_cbh` is set to `False`). The LCL is calculated from surface measurements of pressure, temperature and humidity. In this particular case, the LCL is set as CBH for the cloud around 06:30 and not the observed CBH at about 2 km altitude because the Virga-Sniffer configuration option `cbh_connect2top` is set to `False`. Since all range gates between the LCL, which fills the gap of the lowest CBH layer, and the second CBH layer with the Cloudnet CBH, have a radar signal, the lowest CBH layer is selected by the Virga-Sniffer due to this option. In the CBH processing, CBH layer with similar altitudes (within the threshold `cbh_layer_thres` of 1000 m in the Virga-Sniffer configuration used for BCO data processing) are merged by using their mean altitude value. Reducing the threshold value of `cbh_layer_thres` to a lower value would result in a high number of CBH layers if the ceilometer CBH fluctuates strongly.

Figure 1. BCO case study of 2 December 2021: Cloudnet target classification in panel (a) and Virga-Sniffer output in panel (b). The filled cloud base refers to time steps where the calculated LCL is used to fill the CBH gaps. Haze echoes from the Virga-Sniffer output are unclassified, with radar reflectivities lower than -50 dBZ. Rain reaching the surface is marked in blue along the x-axis.

2.2 Precipitation and Haze echo identification

The detection of precipitation, clouds, and cloud top height (CTH) is performed by analyzing radar signals. Precipitation is identified at each range gate of the radar reflectivity mask below CBH. The process involves downward assignment from the CBH until the lowest radar signal. The downward assignment is continued until the gap larger than the specified threshold of 150 m is encountered. This ensures that tilted fall streaks and vertically separated cloud layers are captured, as vertical gaps due to tilted fall streaks are usually smaller than 150 m while clouds are separated by larger gaps. This of course cannot capture all cases of tilted fall streaks in general, but for our dataset it serves as a good compromise by visual confirmation.

Rain at the surface is detected based on the radar reflectivity dataset. A radar-based surface rain flag is set if Z_e is larger than 0 dBZ in the first radar range gate. Additionally, surface rain information is obtained from the rain flag in the Cloudnet data, which incorporates measurements of the MRR. Data from a distrometer was not always available between July 2021 and July 2023, and thus was not included in the analysis.

Virga is detected primarily from the CBH and radar reflectivity information, but refined through the incorporation of cloud radar mean Doppler velocity data. The amount of pixels identified as virga during the time from 1 July 2021 until 1 July 2022 is visible in the 2D-Histogram of the radar reflectivity factor and mean Doppler velocity in Fig. 2). Virga is identified for all pixels that neither fulfills the criteria of the clutter-mask ($mask_clutter$) nor the velocity-mask ($mask_V_m$). The velocity-mask restricts virga to falling hydrometeors (negative mean Doppler velocities). Consequently, drizzle drops with comparable terminal

velocity to the expected updrafts will not be identified as virga. The refinement of the clutter-mask is achieved through the parameter values, $clutter_m$ and $clutter_c$. Data points labeled as clutter have to fulfill the following conditions:

$$V_m < -m \cdot (Z_e/67(\text{dBZ})) - c \quad (1)$$

with $m = -8$ ($clutter_m$) and $c = -6$ ($clutter_c$). The radar reflectivity factor Z_e is scaled by 67 dBZ, as -67 dBZ represents the minimum reflectivity measured by the CORAL cloud radar during the time from 1 July 2021 until 1 July 2022.

As it can be seen in Fig. 2, a large number of data points show radar reflectivities below -50 dBZ with mean Doppler velocities ranging between ± 2 m s^{-1} . We attribute these radar signals, also termed haze echoes, to originate from hygroscopically grown sea salt aerosols and not virga as mentioned by Klingebiel et al. (2019). It is important to consider that evaporating drizzle drops may exhibit radar reflectivities comparable to those of sea salt aerosols in downdrafts. As a result, the clutter-mask configuration 1 is defined in a balanced manner, capturing both haze echoes in downdrafts and evaporating drizzle instances when Doppler velocities are negative. As it can be seen in Fig. 3, changing the clutter-mask to $m = -55$ and $c = -38$ (configuration 4) reduces the number of pixels identified virga and increases the number of pixels identified as clutter (or haze echoes) for negative mean Doppler velocities.

Here, the Virga-Sniffer is utilized to identify haze echoes that fulfill the condition of the clutter-mask (configuration 1) and have radar reflectivities below -50 dBZ. Finally, all radar pixels that are not identified as precipitation, cloud, or haze echoes remain unclassified. Note that haze echoes have not been observed by Kalesse-Los et al. (2023) for the measurements over the RV *Meteor* due to the lower sensitivity of the 94 GHz which has a minimum valid reflectivity value of -60 dBZ.

3 Warm cloud definition

The configurations of the Virga-Sniffer tool are designed to detect warm clouds. Warm clouds are defined as clouds with bases and tops below the height of the 0°C wet-bulb temperature isotherm that is taken from data of the Cloudnet target categorization. Similar to Kalesse-Los et al. (2023), we further separate into warm clouds with CBH below 1 km (i.e., trade wind cumuli), and clouds with bases and tops above the height of the 0°C wet-bulb temperature isotherm (cold clouds). Please note that Kalesse-Los et al. (2023) simply relied on CBH lower than 4 km for warm-cloud identification (according to mean freezing levels of 4.8 km over RV *Meteor* during EUREC⁴A) which will lead to differences in statistical results compared to our study. The temperature criterium

Figure 2. BCO 35 GHz cloud radar (1 July 2021 – 1 July 2022): Histograms of the mean Doppler velocity V_m and radar reflectivity factor. Data points from the grey-shaded areas are not considered as virga. The velocity mask (mask_Vm) restricts virga events to falling hydrometeors. The choice of the clutter-mask configuration $l(\text{mask_clutter})$ determines the number of pixels classified as haze echos. Radar reflectivity bin width is 1 dBZ and the Doppler velocity bin width 0.1 m s^{-1} . Panel (b) and panel (c) represent the same histogram as in panel (a) but zoomed in for different intervals of the radar reflectivity factor.

Figure 3. BCO 35 GHz cloud radar (1 July 2021 – 1 July 2022): Like in Fig. 2 but for clutter-mask (configuration 4)

is based on the Cloudnet target categorization scheme as falling ice melts when the wet-bulb temperature becomes

positive rather than the actual air temperature (Hogan and O'Connor, 2004). Lidar-derived ice-nucleating particle concentration over Barbados indicates that immersion freezing starts to take place at temperatures lower than -10°C (Haarig et al., 2019; Harrison et al., 2022). BCO Cloudnet observations during EUREC⁴A show that deeper trade wind cumuli often had tops just barely exceeding the height of the 0°C -wet-bulb temperature isotherm. Thus, for the comparison of the EUREC⁴A datasets obtained at BCO and RV *Meteor*, the temperature criterium was relaxed to -10°C to enable a higher comparability to the cloud statistics over RV *Meteor* derived by Kalesse-Los et al. (2023).

4 Comparison between object-based and profile-based statistics

In order to investigate precipitation properties of warm clouds and haze echo occurrence an object-based cloud classifier was developed for the BCO (Roschke et al., 2024). The object-based method in this context stands for an approach to identify continuous radar signals in time and space (connected pixels). Once a cloud object has been detected, information about the CBH can be analyzed within this object. In contrast, profile-based cloud identification relies on the number of detected cloud base heights (CBH). The statistical results in the study of Kalesse-Los et al. (2023) are profile-based.

To relate the following statistics and allow a better comparison between the BCO and RV *Meteor* observations, the object-based detection method was also applied to the RV *Meteor* observations during the EUREC⁴A campaign. Also, for the first time, we obtain long-term statistics from the Virga-Sniffer at the BCO.

4.1 Cloud identification

A comparison between the CBHs detected with the Virga-Sniffer tool and the number of time steps in which a cloud object was detected can be seen in Table 2. From July 2021 to July 2023, the Virga-Sniffer identified 93 % of all CBHs from trade wind cumuli and 85 % of warm clouds. 40 % of all clouds with bases or tops above the height of the 0° wet-bulb temperature isotherm (cold clouds) are recognized by the Virga-Sniffer. There are likely two reasons for the lower proportion of detected cold clouds. Firstly, the ceilometer signal is attenuated in liquid layers. Consequently, in multi-layered cloud situations, the ceilometer detects the cloud base of trade wind cumuli and misses a larger proportion of CBHs from stratiform clouds, mixed-phase clouds, or ice clouds that lie above in the same profile. With the Virga-Sniffer tool, it is possible to fill gaps in cloud bases as part of the CBH preprocessing (see Table 1). The `cbh_fill_limit` is set to 60s in this study, whereby CBH gaps smaller than this time window are filled

by linear interpolation (`cbh_fill_method`). Increasing the time window thus increases the detection range, but can also lead to unphysical CBH results and false-positive detection of virga (Kalesse-Los et al., 2023). The second explanation for the lower proportion of cold clouds detected by the Virga-Sniffer tool is therefore related to the configuration chosen for the BCO dataset.

4.2 EUREC⁴A statistics at the BCO and the RV *Meteor*

Table 4 gives an overview of Virga-Sniffer derived statistics of clouds, precipitation, and haze echoes for BCO and RV *Meteor* during EUREC⁴A. The RV *Meteor* profile-based results show an 8 % lower proportion of warm clouds compared to the RV *Meteor* object-based results. This difference can be explained by two facts: One, in the object-based approach, the temperature threshold to differentiate between warm and cold clouds is -10°C . Using a temperature criterium of 0°C , reduces the proportion of warm clouds to 76 % and the proportion of rain reaching the ground to 7 % in this case. Second, within the profile-based approach, only single profiles with CBH below 4 km are considered as warm clouds. In Kalesse-Los et al. (2023) the Virga-Sniffer tool is configured to replace the lowest CBH layer by the calculated LCL. Consequently, also profiles with gaps in the CBH layer (e.g. due to strong attenuation of the ceilometer by rain) are considered in the profile-based statistic. This would also explain the higher proportion of trade wind cumuli in Kalesse-Los et al. (2023) compared to the object-based results for the RV *Meteor*. The comparison of profile- and object-based approaches illustrates the influence of the Virga-Sniffer configuration on the statistical results.

5 Longterm and seasonal statistics at the BCO

Tab. 3 gives an overview of Virga-Sniffer derived statistics of clouds, precipitation, and haze echoes for BCO covering the time period between 1 July 2021 until 1 July 2023 and RV *Meteor* during EUREC⁴A. While these statistics are partly presented in Roschke et al. (2024), this section focuses on the differences in statistical results related to the Virga-Sniffer configurations and cloud classification methods.

The object-based detection method revealed a 10 %-increase in warm cloud identification, and a 6 % decrease of trade wind cumuli occurrence of trade wind cumuli. Consequently, the proportion of virga originating from warm clouds using the object-based method is lower compared to the profile-based method, as more clouds are taken into account in the former. The proportion of precipitation-producing trade wind cumuli for the object-based detection method is notably lower compared to the profile-based detection method. This indicates that a large proportion of precipitation identified below trade wind cumuli for the profile-based method is counted as precipitation from warm clouds

Table 2. Proportion of different cloud classes in % from the Virga-Sniffer compared to the number of time steps where a cloud object was detected. Cold clouds denote clouds with CBH or CTH above the height of the 0 °C wet-bulb temperature isotherm. Periods of observation from July 2021 until July 2022 (2021/22) with the wet and dry season for this period are below. For July 2022 until July 2023 (2022/23) the same applies for the wet and the dry season. The two years from July 2021 until July 2023 are denoted as "2021/23".

	Trade wind cumuli	Warm clouds	Cold clouds	All clouds
2021/22	96	86	42	63
Wet season	100	89	42	60
Dry season	92	85	42	65
2022/23	90	84	38	54
Wet season	88	80	36	48
Dry season	91	88	40	64
2021/23	93	85	40	59

for the object-based detection method. The reason for these differences is related to the CBH configurations of the Virga-Sniffer and the different approaches to cloud classification. For the profile-based detection method, single profiles within a warm cloud object, identified by the object-based method, can be counted as trade wind cumuli by the profile-based method based on the location of the CBH below 1 km. These profiles with CBH lower than 1 km are simply omitted for the object-based method if they occur within a warm-cloud object.

A summary of the seasonal Virga-Sniffer statistics is provided in Table 4. The seasonal statistics form a possible reference value for future statistics that quantify the occurrence of virga.

Code and data availability. The source code of the haze echo classification (Roschke, 2024a, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10469906>, v1.0.1) and cloud classification algorithm (Roschke, 2024b, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10471932>, v1.0.1) is freely available and hosted on Zenodo. The BCO data are freely available to the broader community upon request. Cloudnet processing was done using CloudnetPy (Tukiainen et al., 2022, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7432587>, v1.43.0).

Author contributions. This publication is based on the master thesis written by JR which was supervised by HKL and MH. JR developed the haze echo classification and cloud classification algorithm, performed the CloudnetPy processing and Virga-Sniffer processing of the BCO data, used the Virga-Sniffer output for analysis of the BCO and RV *Meteor* EUREC⁴A data, derived the statistics of the Cloudnet target classification data and contributed mostly to the writing of the manuscript. HKL was in charge of the project management and operation of the instruments of Leipzig University on board RV *Meteor* during EUREC⁴A. JW performed the Virga-Sniffer processing and statistics for additional configurations of the Virga-Sniffer for the EUREC⁴A dataset. HKL, MH, MK, JW, AF and AK contributed to discussions and editing of the manuscript. AK gave valuable feedback regarding the Virga-Sniffer statistics.

Competing interests. The contact author has declared that none of the authors has any competing interests.

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Table 3. Virga-Sniffer statistics in % during the EUREC⁴A campaign between 18 January 2020 and 19 February 2020 over the BCO and the RV *Meteor*. The results are derived for different Virga-Sniffer configurations that are described in Table 1. Warm cloud and trade wind cumuli identification are performed using an object-based (ob) and a profile-based (pb) detection method. The statistics from the RV *Meteor*, using the profile-based approach and configuration 0 represent the results conducted by Kalesse-Los et al. (2023).

Platform	BCO	RV <i>Meteor</i>	RV <i>Meteor</i>	RV <i>Meteor</i>	RV <i>Meteor</i>
Number of days:	26	28	28	28	28
N total cloud timesteps:	34k	34k	358k	411k	484k
Configuration	1	0	0	2	3
Detection method	ob	ob	pb	pb	pb
Warm clouds ...	71	81	73	79	73
... producing precipitation:	47	44	56	51	50
... producing rain reaching the surface:	5	10	14	12	10
... producing virga:	42	34	42	39	40
... with haze echoes (without/ with virga in the same profile)	43/60	7/11	-	-	-
Fraction of virga from trade wind cumuli:	70	31	56	48	24
... that are trade wind cumuli:	78	49	63	59	40
Trade wind cumuli ...	56	40	46	46	29
... producing precipitation:	44	29	59	49	37
... producing rain reaching the surface:	6	7	22	17	13
... producing virga:	38	22	37	32	24
... with haze echoes (without/ with virga in the same profile)	49/70	10/12	-	-	-

Table 4. Virga-Sniffer Statistics in (%) for the dry and the wet season between July 2021 until July 2022 (2021/22) and July 2022 until July 2023 (2022/23). Precipitation and haze echoes are taken into account when CBH from warm clouds or trade wind cumuli are detected above. Haze echoes are filtered out when virga is detected in the same profile. The detection method object base (ob) is used for the BCO data set.

period of observation	07/2021	Wet season	Dry season	07/2022	Wet season	Dry season	07/2020
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	07/2022	2021/22	2021/22	07/2023	2022/23	2022/23	07/2023
Platform	BCO						
Number of days	268	112	156	240	129	111	508
Detection method	ob						
Number of total cloud time steps	397k	159k	238k	342k	184k	158k	739k
Fraction of clouds from clear sky	51	49	53	50	49	50	50
Warm clouds ...	65	57	70	56	40	68	61
... producing precipitation	51	47	54	43	40	45	48
... producing rain reaching the surface	4	4	4	2	3	2	3
... producing virga	47	43	50	41	37	43	44
... with haze echoes (without/ with virga in the same profile)	40/65	46/69	37/63	43/62	42/63	43/64	41/64
Fraction of virga from trade wind cumuli	67	81	60	69	77	64	56
... that are trade wind cumuli	74	86	68	75	81	70	68
Trade wind cumuli ...	48	49	48	42	37	47	45
... producing precipitation	47	45	48	40	38	41	44
... producing rain reaching the surface	4	4	4	2	3	2	3
... producing virga	43	41	44	38	35	39	40
... with haze echoes (without/ with virga in the same profile)	50/74	51/74	49/74	50/68	47/63	53/68	50/71

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